

CULTURAL DIPLOMACY AND NIGERIA'S RELATIONS WITH ASIA

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Abstract

The economic relations between Nigeria and Asia has given rise to multi-faceted socio-cultural relations. Over the years, Nigeria has grown in space with economic activities at the centre stage of its bilateral relations with other sovereign nations, the world over. While it is a truism that Nigeria's establishment of diplomatic ties with Asia is in furtherance of her efforts to promote and strengthen the objectives of South-South cooperation which among other things, is aimed at promoting cooperation among countries of the Southern Hemisphere in a wide range of areas such as trade, investment, technical cooperation, industrialization, energy, food and agriculture, and technology; the pattern of bilateral interaction between Nigeria and Asia has impacted markedly on the area of cultural diplomacy. Pertinent questions however are to what extent has Nigeria involved in cultural diplomacy with the countries of Asia? What are the contending issues and benefits arising from such cultural relations? Using China and Malaysia as a case in point for analysis, the study interrogates this and other variegated issues arising from Nigeria-Asia cultural relations. Essentially, the paper argues and also demonstrates that despite some challenges, Nigeria has been able to benefit from cultural relations with Asia. The paper adopts a multidisciplinary frame of analysis employing both descriptive and narrative tools at arriving at a conclusion.

Introduction

Genuine intellectual discourse in contemporary international relations will not be complete without taking into cognizance the place of culture as a crucial component in inter-state relations.

This is based on the fact that the global society itself is a composition of diverse cultural identities with long histories that predate the current age.¹ Culture plays

¹ G.I. Sheriff, E. Adie and N.L. Obiagelli
"Nigeria-China Cultural Relations: Harnessing

key role in the enhancement of the image of a country by directing the perception of its recipients to areas that will enable a better understanding of its values.² This explains the imperativeness of cultural relations among independent nations of the world. Through cultural exchange, individuals from distinct cultural backgrounds can also learn to appreciate and cherish the values in other cultures. As a matter of fact, the volume of human relations, (internationally), drastically increased and consequently, ideas, values, customs, culture and attitudes of societies became diffused across international borders necessitating cultural relations among independent nations of the world. Indeed, the emergence of sovereign states and the later interdependence of same further create the opportunity for cultural relations across borders. Unarguably, the interdependence of sovereign states has intensified the unification of the world peoples into one orbit and increased inter-state relations with culture serving as platform for such relations. For Nigeria, her contact with the outside

the Potentials for Tourism and National Development” in *Nile Journal of Political Science*, Vol. 1(2), 2019, pp.15 – 16

² D. Stelowski “Culture in International Relations: Defining Cultural Diplomacy” in *Polish Journal of political Science*, Vol. 1, Issue 3, 2015, p.61.

world through the instrumentality of diplomatic ties enhances its cultural relations.

Cultural diplomacy is an integral part of diplomatic activities of almost all states in our days. Although this specific dimension of diplomacy is being attached a growing importance in last decades, it can be still considered the most underestimated area of diplomatic activities of states, particularly in comparison with economic or defence diplomacy. Therefore, an aspect of diplomatic relationship that is of great importance cannot be said to be inconsequential and unworthy of intellectual interpretations. This informs the exigency for this research. Besides, culture has been adjudged as “a powerful global economic engine generating jobs and income with a value of US\$1.3 trillion in 2005”, while in 2007 forty percent of global tourism revenue is said to have come from cultural tourism.³ Against this backdrop, by the end of 2010, China, Asia’s demographic giant, declared its new plan for a strategic partnership with Nigeria, featuring “political equality and cultural

³ UNESCO “The Power of Culture for Development”. France: UNESCO, 2010. Retrieved online from http://www.lacult.unesco.org/lacult_en/doc/The_Power_of_Culture_Developmet.pdf

relations”⁴, which forms the thrust of this article. The study seeks to identify the crucial aspects of Nigeria-Asia cultural interactions, assess the receptivity of Asia’s penetration of Nigerian culture and the changing perspective on the viability of the bilateral relations. To achieve this purpose, the paper proceeds in segments as follows: introduction; conceptual and theoretical issues; a historical overview of Nigeria-Asia cultural relations, contending issues in Nigeria-Asia cultural relations; discussion; and conclusion.

Conceptual and Theoretical Issues

The concept used in this study that demands clarification for better understanding of the argument here is the concept of cultural diplomacy. Perhaps, the concept of cultural diplomacy would be better captured with a fore understanding of the terms culture (which is explained in terms of the tradition of a people, their arts, customs, and beliefs), and the concept of diplomacy. According to *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, culture “is the beliefs, way of life, art, and customs that are shared and

⁴ M. Egbula and Q. Zheng “China and Nigeria: A Powerful South-South Alliance” in *The Sahel and West Africa Club Secretariat*, 2011, p.5.

accepted by people in a particular society”⁵.

By the above definition it means that culture entails the totality of a people’s way of life which include, but not limited to, their dietary habit, religion and worship system, mode of dress, burial system, technology, marriage and civilization. In this wise, Uchendu observes that culture is the basic idea that gives a society its identity and binds it into one.⁶ The Nigerian Cultural Policy categorized culture into material and non-material forms. The former refers to physical items such as beads, bracelets, and clothes that are associated with a group of persons, while non-material culture refers to the ideals, norms and values of a given people.⁷

The term diplomacy is given to several meanings and interpretations by scholars of international relations and politics such that none is generally accepted in explaining the concept.

⁵ *Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English*, 6th Ed. (Essex: Pearson Education Limited), 2014, p.432.

⁶ Uchendu quoted in W.T. Uji “Cultural Awakening: A Tool for National Development” in *Benue Valley Journal of Humanities*, Vol.3, No.2, 2000, p.51.

⁷ E. Essien and S. Iorza “Global Media and Cultural Domination: Strategies for a New World Information and Communication Order (NWICO) for Africa” in *Journal of Globalization and International Studies*, Vol.4, No.1&2, 2009, p.71.

Diplomacy is both “a category of practice and a category of analysis”⁸, meaning that contemporary definitions of diplomacy are broad and differentiated along epistemological and methodological boundaries. A charming characterization, although heavily criticized, is given by Satow⁹ who defines diplomacy as the application of intelligence and tact to the conduct of official relations between the government of independent states. McDermott¹⁰, another leading scholar in international relations sees diplomacy as, “a science which permits its practitioners to say nothing and to shelter behind mysterious nods of the head [...] a science whose most successful exponent is he who can swim with his head above stream of events he pretends to conduct.” More elaborately, Plischke defines diplomacy as “[...] the political process whereby states establish and nurture official inter-relations, direct and indirect, to pursue their respective goals, interest and

substantive and procedural policies in the international environment.”¹¹

For the purpose of our analysis, diplomacy is conceptualized to mean the political process by which political entities, generally states, conduct official relations with one another within an international environment. It is a mechanism designed to establish and maintain networks and relationships among traditional and new actors in the pursuit of shared interdependent goals.¹²

Arising from the above analysis on the concept of diplomacy, cultural diplomacy is therefore conceptualized here to mean, the promotion of cooperation among cultural subjects from the sending state and the receiving state. In practice, this can be carried out mostly by means of providing information to cultural subjects in one (sending) state on the possibilities of establishing contacts and cooperation with “parallel” cultural subjects in the second (receiving) state and vice versa.¹³

⁸ V. Pouliot and J. Cornut “Practice Theory and the Study of Diplomacy: A Research Agenda” in *Cooperation and Conflict*, Vol.50, No.3, 2015, p.299.

⁹ E. Satow *A Guide to Diplomatic Practice* (London: Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd), 1966, p.1.

¹⁰ G. McDermott *The New Diplomacy and its Approaches* (London: Plume Press/Ward Lock Ltd), 1973, p.37.

¹¹ E. Plischke *Microstate the World Affairs: Policy Problems and Options* (Washington DC: American Enterprises Institute for Public Policy Research), 1977, p.41.

¹² D. Hart and A. Siniver “The Meaning of Diplomacy” in *International Negotiation*, 26, 2020, p.6.

¹³ G.R. Berridge and A. James *A Dictionary of Diplomacy*, 2nd Ed. (Hampshire and New York: Palgrave Macmillan), 2003, p.63.

The theoretical framework adopted in this study as a frame of analysis is the systems theory. Developed in the 1950s, the theory provides a useful basis for both theoretical and practical analysis. The main proponents of the theory are James Rosenau, McClelland, Morton Kaplan, and Karl W. Deutsch. Rosenau, one of the proponents of the theory has suggested that “systemic research be pursued not only in terms of local, national and international systems but also in terms of issue areas”.¹⁴ Its underlying assumption is that there is order or system in international relations. It sees nations as being in continuous contact in intricate framework of relationships resulting from the process of interactions,¹⁵ just as Nigeria is interacting with the countries of Asia through cultural relations.

A nation’s behaviour, according to McClelland, is a two-way activity of taking from, and giving to, the international environment;¹⁶ this is the

¹⁴ N.D. Palmer and H.C. Perkins *International Relations: The World Community in Transition, 3rd Revised Edition* (Delhi: A.I.T.B.S. Publishers), 2007, p.xix

¹⁵ E. Agubamah and Z.T. Zasha “China’s Cultural Diplomacy in Africa: The Trajectories, Trends and Realities” in *Journal of African Politics and Society*, Vol.2, No.2, 2013, p.171.

¹⁶ C. Chandra *The Analysis of Systems Theory* (Beijing: Agna Press), 1986.

main aim of Nigeria’s (cultural) relations with Asia. The system theory also emphasizes the significance of the interaction of behaviours of states just as this study is centered on Nigeria’s cultural diplomacy in the country’s relations with China and Malaysia. The system’s theory also views international environment as a result of diverse actions. International relationships are conceived as the consequences of vast number of particular purposes, intentions, expectations and efforts.¹⁷ As the system theory correctly posits, the purposes, intentions, and expectations of Nigeria and Asia in their cultural relations are to promote and maintain cultural contact, hence the suitability of this theory for this study.

Nigeria-Asia Cultural Relations: An Analysis

Nigeria has engaged in diplomatic relationship with the countries of Asia, beginning with the country’s independence in 1960. In this section therefore, an analysis of Nigeria’s cultural relations with Asia is critically examined. Because analyzing Asia in its entirety will be too ambiguous, the study uses China and Malaysia as a case in

¹⁷ E. Agubamah and Z.T. Zasha “China’s Cultural Diplomacy in Africa: The Trajectories, Trends and Realities”...2013, p.171

point for analysis. Culturally, Chibundu reveals that the country's first official diplomacy with Asia came with Nigeria hosting the Anhui Acrobatic Troupe from China in the first quarter of 1980 which China reciprocated by hosting Nigeria Women Basketball team who were in China for two weeks play tour. According to him, cultural exchange between the two countries, further received a boost following series of exhibitions on the economic and cultural life and the performance of Acrobatic troupes from China at the National Theatre in 1983 and 1985 respectively. He also noted that the exchange of visits by the two countries' Ministers of culture in 1983 and 1984 were most significant as they facilitated the signing of two enabling working programmes by their representatives.¹⁸ Thus, the Chinese delegation led by Vice Minister of culture in 1983 signed the cultural programme for 1983-1984. In November 1984 Nigeria's Minister of culture visited China in return to sign the 1985-1986 cultural programme whose implementation has helped to strengthen the relationship between the two countries as Nigeria hosted Chinese

¹⁸ V.N. Chibundu *Nigeria-China Foreign Relations, 1960-1999* (Ibadan: Spectrum Books Limited), 2000, p.46.

photo exhibition at the Iganmu National Theatre, Lagos and three Chinese study groups on research tour to Lagos, Benin and Zaria in 1987.¹⁹

According to Udeala²⁰, on 28th March, 1990, a new accord, the Cultural and Educational Cooperation was signed by Nigeria and China. The implementation of this accord saw the performance of Chinese song, music and Acrobatic troupe as well as films, painting, and carving exhibition in Nigeria. However, it was observed that Nigeria did not reciprocate the gesture by going to China to perform and display its rich culture as China did in Nigeria. This necessitated the signing of the protocol for the implementation of the Cultural and Educational Cooperation between Nigeria and China (1997-1999) in 1997. Suffice it to say that cultural contacts between Nigeria and China have been on the increase as many Nigerians acknowledge the country's long-term links with China, and the presence of a huge Chinese community in Nigeria.²¹

¹⁹ V.N. Chibundu *Nigeria-China Foreign Relations, 1960-1999...2000*, pp.47-48.

²⁰ S.O. Udeala "Nigeria-China Economic Relations Under the South-South Cooperation" in *Journal of international Affairs*, Vol.13, No.1&2, 2010, p.65.

²¹ A. Aloa "Nigeria and the BRICs: Diplomatic, Trade, Cultural and Military Relations" in The

Another aspect of Nigeria cultural diplomacy with the countries of Asia is through the Nigeria-Malaysia relationship. In the pursuit of social and cultural integration, the two countries took special interest in their affairs by introducing a number of measures to achieve this goal. The two nations support the exchange of experiences and information on literacy, professional training and employment, mutual cooperation in the promotion of sporting activities with a view to bringing together the youths of Nigeria and Malaysia and ensuring their balanced development. Likewise, both nations support promoting a continuous strengthened cooperation amongst themselves in health matters and related fields.²² This relation has helped both countries in the setting up of a number of associations within their jurisdictions. For example, the Nigeria–Malaysia accords have occasionally attracted football competition under the aegis the West African and South East Asia Football Union.

Besides, in order to facilitate the promotion and development of cultural

integration, Nigeria and Malaysia signed Economic, Scientific, Technical and Cultural Cooperation Agreement (ESTC) in 1990, which was aimed at fostering cooperation in areas of science and technology, culture, economy, and capacity building.²³ To this end, member states pursue the promotion of learning and dissemination of a language as a factor in community integration and unity; establish where necessary, structures and mechanisms for the production, propagation and utilization of cultural industries within the area of agreement. Moreover, in March 2001, Nigeria signed a Declaration on the Principles of Friendly Relations, Partnership and a Programme on Cultural and Scientific Cooperation with Malaysia.²⁴ It is instructive to stress that Nigeria and Malaysia have common social cultural background with necessitate these cultural contacts.

Furthermore, as part of the public diplomacy programme of the High Commission, the ASEAN Film Festival was successfully held at the Korean

South African Institute of International Affairs (SAII), Occasional Paper No. 101, 2011, p.25.

²² C.A. Kezie and B.H. Amir “Economics Cross-Roads: The Experiences of Nigeria and Lessons from Malaysia” in *Journal of Development and Agricultural Economics*. Vol. 3(8), 2011, p.368

²³ I. Bello “An Appraisal of Malaysia-Nigeria Foreign Economic Relations” in *European Academic Research*, Vol. V, Issue 1, 2017, p.758.

²⁴ O.I. Eme “Unemployment Rate in Nigeria: Agenda for Government” in *Academic Journal of Interdisciplinary Studies* (Rome-Italy: MCSER Publishing), 2014, p.12.

Cultural Centre in Abuja from 19 to 26 April 2017. The event was co-hosted by other ASEAN missions in Abuja, namely Indonesia, the Philippines, Thailand and Viet Nam. The festival was also part of the programme spearheaded by the ASEAN Community in Abuja (ACA) to commemorate the 50th anniversary of the establishment of ASEAN. The event was delightfully graced by representatives and participants from the two countries. During the course of the event, Malaysia's movie entitled "Nota" was screened. Audience at the event were estimated to be around 200 people. Prior to the screening, several Malaysian delicacies prepared by Perwakilan members such as *karipap*, *pulut kuning*, *kuih keria*, *kuih bakar*, *agar-agar* and *teh tarik* were served.²⁵ The event serves as breeding ground for cross cultural diplomacy between Nigeria and Malaysia.

Contending Issues in Nigeria-Asia Cultural Relations

Development experts and scholars especially historians, political scientists and cultural anthropologists have often criticized Europe for under-developing

Africa. While these allegations are cogent, given Africa's unsavoury history of slave trade, colonialism and neo-colonialism, the growing relations with Asia raises a spectre which if, not addressed urgently, might lead future scholars to grumble again, this time about how Asia underdeveloped Africa. The current trend in Nigeria-Asia relations is laden with strategic cooperation and collaboration as well as mutual cooperation.²⁶ However, a dispassionate analysis of cultural diplomacy shows an equation that replicates a similar one the West had with Africa which led to cultural imperialism. Using China as a point of discussion Liu captures it that:

The broad outline and intended goal of China's Cultural Visitor Programme was to promote mutual cultural understanding,... the intention and the underlying assumption were very prominent...and the goal had also been transformed from tentative cultural understanding to cultural industry cooperation...Culture in its own right was discussed only when it might go against development and as something to be mobilised as a valuable

²⁵ Malaysia Connect "Cultural Diplomacy through Film: 2nd ASEAN Film Festival In Abuja, 19-26 April 2017" Official Newsletter Vol. 1, Jan-June 2017, pp.1-5.

²⁶ S.O. Udeala "Nigeria-China Economic Relations under the South-South Cooperation" in *African Journal of International Affairs*, Vol.13, No.1&2, 2010, 78.

resource for development. This trend is a logical extension of the priority of the present Chinese domestic cultural policy: to develop the cultural industry.²⁷

From the above submission, there is no doubt that Africa's market for Asia's cultural products is still very uncertain. Objectively, the language and cultural barriers to be conquered within the trade in cultural products are huge.

Given Asia's standing, it is surprising and worrying that culture does not receive more attention across governments and that, as a nation, we are under-investing in our cultural infrastructure, which has given Asia an edge over Nigeria. If our cultural institutions are to maintain the inspirational role that they have, we need to replenish and nurture them. Cultural connections and cultural relations cannot be sustained in the face of threatened funding cuts. Some of our institutions are unable to add contemporary work to their collections and repertory and so cannot reflect the changing makeup of our own society, let alone maintain their position

²⁷ H. Liu "China-Africa Relations through the Prism of Culture – The Dynamics of China's Cultural Diplomacy with Africa" in *Journal of Current Chinese Affairs, China aktuell*, 3, 2008, p.27.

as an up-to-date global resource relevant to balance our relations with Asia.

Another major challenge of Nigeria-Asia cultural diplomacy is in the area of language understanding. Language constitutes an important aspect of culture that not only enhances but facilitates cultural relations. Language apart from been a symbol of cultural identity, is a medium with which people communicate and interact with others. Without language, it is impossible for people of different cultures to interact with one another. Anyogo describes language as "an umbilical cord or better still, a facebook web that connects people of different origins, races, cultures etc in the world."²⁸ With the benefit of language understanding, it becomes easy for parties to interact in a web of intergroup relations even across national borders. However, given that there exists a difficulty by majority of Nigerians to speak and understand Asian languages during cultural interface, the benefit of cultural diplomacy has continued to elude Nigeria. This explains why the Chinese economic attaché once remarked that [...] "China finds it easier to bring some Chinese workers like Managers,

²⁸ C. Anyogo "Language, Literature, Education and Crisis Management in Nigeria's Democratic Experience" in *Journal of African Politics and Society*, Vol.1, No.2, 2012, p.143.

Accountants and Secretaries who could send the report of the progress of the work back to Chinese government or the home company written in Chinese language...until Nigerians are able to understand Chinese language”.²⁹

Nevertheless, with the establishment of Confucius Institutes in some Nigerian universities by Chinese government, it is hoped that the challenge of language will soon be overcome. In order to achieve this feat, more of these institutions should be established in all tertiary institutions of the country. More important is that for Nigeria to benefit the more from its cultural relations Asian languages should be taught at post-primary school level since such will benefit Nigeria.

Another contending issue in Nigeria-Asia cultural relations is the creation of Chinese separate towns in some Nigerian cities for example, Lagos. The creation of separate residential areas for Chinese people in Nigerian towns will not encourage harmonious interactions between Nigeria and China, just like Malaysia, rather, it will encourage separatist tendencies. As well as the case during the period of Nigeria’s colonial

experience, the establishment of separate town for China would possibly arouse resentment in a way which would affect the nature of relationship between Nigeria and China through cultural interface. This is possible, should the people in the cities in which Chinatown is established begin to feel that government is not interested in the plight of the local people like their Chinese counterpart especially, the disparity in the availability of basic social amenities. Indeed, the separation of Chinese from the rest of Nigerians has the tendency of generating ethnic exclusiveness and particularism which is unhealthy for cultural relations.

Unequal economic development between Nigeria and countries of Asia constitutes another impediment to cultural relations between them. It should be borne in mind that Nigeria-Asia ties are premised on economic factor; cultural relations seem to be an added impetus to these robust bilateral ties. Given that Nigeria’s economic growth as a third world country is not at par with that of Asia, there is every tendency that in near future, the Asian culture will subsume that of Nigeria since the economy is the defining factor in international relations in the contemporary period. Therefore, in order for Nigeria to benefit immensely from her cultural relations with Asia,

²⁹ A. Osundu “China’s Unconditional Aid: For or Against Nigeria’s Development?” in *VUNA Journal of History and International Relations*, Vol.1, No.1, 2013, p.335

emphasis should be placed on developing Nigeria's economy that is capable of competing with the rest of the world.

Conclusion

The intense interconnectedness of the global system and its far-reaching implications on the policies of a state, in relation to other states, necessitates the establishment of some degree of strategy by the state in its interactions with others for the pursuit of crucial interests. The means through which such relationship is conducted is called diplomacy, and it arises out of the coexistence of a multitude of independent states in an inter-dependent world.³⁰ For Nigeria's interests, in the context of diplomacy, to be optimally promoted, the country need to adopt activist stance in public policies involving the arts and culture. This requires an understanding of how culture affects our relations with other countries and our competitiveness in the world economy. Apart from this, the country needs to acknowledge her allies' concerns about culture when negotiating international economic interests. Finally,

³⁰ L. Lawal and M.H. Daiyabu "Developmental Diplomacy in a Globalised World: The Imperatives of Soft Power in Nigeria's External Relations under the Transformation Agenda of President Goodluck Jonathan" in *International Affairs and Global Strategy*, Vol.28, 2015, p.5

the country needs to be attentive to how cultural diplomacy is organized. It is the opinion of this paper that the best way to evoke cultural awareness and guarantee the required intercultural competence is international training. Only in this way can diplomats cultivate cultural intelligence and learn how to communicate cross-culturally.

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